

Deliverable D1.6

Media Guide

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Change Log

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v1	28.10.2025	Rafael Diaz	Initial draft

Acronyms and Abbreviations

DX.X	Deliverable
EIC	European Innovation Council
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ME	Multiphoton Endoscopy
N	Nitrogen
PET	Positron Emission Tomography
PNG, JPG, WEBP, SVG	File formats for digital images, with differences in compression and loss of information
v	Version

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
1. Introduction	4
2. Description of the work	4
2.1. Project description materials	4
2.1.1. Boilerplate text	4
2.1.2. Key messages	5
2.2. Visual and branding instructions	6
2.2.2. Document templates	9
2.2.3. EIC Funding Guidelines	9
2.3. Media handling protocols	11
3. Conclusion	11

Executive Summary

This report outlines the key information and general guidelines for handling media requests and managing the public presence of the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project, both in relation to its establishment and its results. It presents the project's key messages, boilerplate text, visual guidelines, funding acknowledgement requirements, and the general approach to media interactions, which are intended to be followed by all project partners.

1. Introduction

The RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project is part of the European Innovation Council (EIC) through the Pathfinder Open Call and is led by the project coordinator, Euro-BioImaging ERIC. The consortium is a partnership of 9 beneficiaries, with representation of Austria, Italy, Finland, France, and the Netherlands. The project started on 1 May 2025 and continues until April 2028.

RE-IMAGINE-CROPS seeks to transform agricultural practices through innovation in Digital Precision Agronomy. The primary objective of the project is to develop the first mobile imaging technology for in-field measurement of biophysical processes in crops, thereby enabling more effective crop management practices.

A Media Guide provides agreed guidance on how a project communicates with external audiences through interviews, press coverage, social media, and other media activities. It brings together key messages, project descriptions, visual and branding rules, and funding acknowledgement requirements, ensuring that all partners communicate in a consistent and compliant manner.

2. Description of the work

2.1. Project description materials

2.1.1. Boilerplate text

As indicated in Deliverable 1.5, a boilerplate text has been prepared and updated accordingly. The most recent version is also available on the [project website](#):

RE-IMAGINE-CROPS is a Horizon Europe-funded project that brings together leading research institutions, imaging specialists, and agricultural industry partners to advance sustainable crop management. The project focuses on developing the first **real-time, in-field portable** multimodal multiscale imaging system that combines Positron Emission Tomography (PET) with Multiphoton Endoscopy (ME).

This integrated technology will enable precise, non-invasive measurements of plant responses to nitrogen (N) fertiliser at both metabolic and cellular levels directly in the

field. By linking imaging data with plant physiological processes, the project will support the development of optimised fertilisation strategies that reduce ecological impact and improve resource efficiency.

The **goal** of RE-IMAGINE-CROPS is to **tailor fertiliser application** by measuring functional processes that reflect the crop's local and systemic responses shortly after nitrogen delivery. Through this approach, the project aims to contribute to more sustainable and data-driven agricultural practices.

The consortium includes ten partner institutions: *Euro-BioImaging ERIC* (coordination), *BF Educational*, *University of Turku*, *University of Maastricht*, *CNRS* (in connection with the *University of Lille*), *LIGHTCORE Technologies*, *VRVis*, *University of Teramo* and *NOVA.id*; combining expertise in plant science, bioimaging, modelling, and agri-food innovation to ensure both scientific excellence and real-world impact.

2.1.2. Key messages

<p>Objectives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop, prove, and exploit the commercialisation of a novel real-time RE-IMAGINE-CROPS technology for the in-field measurement of biophysical processes in crops • Develop, prove, and exploit the commercialisation of a novel crop management method based on the real-time RE-IMAGINE-CROPS technology for agronomists, scientists and the fertilisers industry
<p>Motivation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop an innovative imaging technology to support more sustainable and efficient crop management, addressing one of agriculture's most pressing challenges: the overuse of nitrogen (N) fertilisers.
<p>Approach</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a mobile prototype integrating PET and endoscopy imaging technologies • Design AI-based software for co-registration of multiscale, multimodal images • Conduct field testing to establish proof-of-concept of the technology
<p>Outcomes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A functional mobile prototype integrating PET and endoscopy imaging technologies • AI-driven software enabling accurate co-registration of multiscale, multimodal images • Multi-omics and phenotypic datasets supporting the interpretation of

	<p>imaging outputs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Validated proof-of-concept demonstrated through rigorous field testing
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2.2. Visual and branding instructions

2.2.1. Guidelines for Logo and Templates

As outlined in Deliverable 1.1, project branding plays an essential role in ensuring clear recognition and consistent dissemination of the project’s message. Although this information was already presented in Deliverable 1.1 when describing the project logo and branding guidelines, it is reiterated here, given its importance for maintaining a coherent visual identity, ensuring effective dissemination of results, and enabling users to easily recognise and follow the project.

The project logo is available in PNG, JPG, WEBP, and SVG formats and is stored in the project’s shared [Google Drive](#). The full-color logo is the preferred option to maintain visual clarity and brand identity. Negative versions should be used when backgrounds are of low contrast, as shown as follows:

The logo must always include a clear space when in use, shown as follows:

Proper usage of the project logo is encouraged. Any modifications or alterations are not permissible, as a coherent identity is easier to share and to follow. The following are examples of alterations that are not permitted:

The logo can be used in one color shade.
Use only Primary Color: #0C6E59

The logo can't use different colors from the colors panel.

Don't stretch the logo.

Don't stretch the logo.

The color palette for the logo, shown below, includes 3 primary colors, 3 secondary colors, and 6 extra colors for accents.

PRIMARY COLORS

HEX #0C6E59
RGB 12 110 89
CMYK 86 30 67 22

HEX #08403F
RGB 8 64 63
CMYK 90 46 58 56

HEX #FFF812
RGB 255 248 18
CMYK 8 0 88 0

SECONDARY COLORS

HEX #052D2B
RGB 5 45 43
CMYK 90 52 63 70

HEX #0F936D
RGB 15 147 109
CMYK 82 17 67 3

HEX #00E599
RGB 0 229 153
CMYK 65 0 57 0

EXTRA COLORS

HEX #3c3056
RGB 60 48 86
CMYK 84 85 35 32

HEX #9775a7
RGB 151 117 167
CMYK 48 59 10 0

HEX #10a6a9
RGB 16 166 169
CMYK 75 9 36 0

HEX #76dbd3
RGB 118 219 211
CMYK 52 0 25 0

HEX #df524a
RGB 223 82 74
CMYK 6 79 67 0

HEX #e59270
RGB 229 146 112
CMYK 8 50 55 0

The fonts chosen for the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS are Figtree for titles and DM Sans for texts (both provided by fonts.google.com).

HEADING TEXT, SEMIBOLD

Revealing the Unseen: Illuminating Life through Bioimaging

HEADING TEXT, MEDIUM

A curious cat named 3 whiskers roamed the 7 hills of Xanadu, exploring the mysteries of pi (π) and the infinite possibilities hidden within the realm of alphanumeric characters.

Figtree (fonts.google.com)

BODY TEXT

Bioimaging is a revolutionary field at the intersection of biology and imaging technology, providing invaluable insights into the intricate structures and dynamic processes within living organisms. Through the lens of cutting-edge imaging techniques, scientists delve into the microscopic realms of cells, tissues, and entire organisms, unraveling the mysteries of life at the molecular level.

A curious cat named 3 whiskers roamed the 7 hills of Xanadu, exploring the mysteries of pi (π) and the infinite possibilities hidden within the realm of **alphanumeric** characters.

DM Sans (fonts.google.com)

2.2.2. Document templates

Dedicated templates have been prepared for project materials, including standard formats for general documents and presentations. These templates follow the EIC guidelines (described below) and are available in the project's shared [Google Drive](#).

2.2.3. EIC Funding Guidelines

In addition to the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS logo, the project partners are also aware of their obligation to acknowledge EU funding and to display the EU emblem in all information and communication

materials. In case of co-branding, the EU funding logo must be featured as prominently and visibly as any other logo in use, as stated in the operational guidelines provided by the European Commission¹.

Whenever the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project is referenced in written materials, such as scientific publications, news items, or other communications, a standard funding acknowledgement of support from the European Union (European Commission) must be included. Examples of acceptable acknowledgement statements are provided below:

- *The RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement ID 101187260.*
- *The RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement ID 101187260. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.*

¹ European Commission, "The Use of the EU Emblem in the Context of EU Programme", (2021) https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/3192a0ef-6bda-4e1a-81ca-65ade2ffad73_en?filename=eu_emblem_rules.pdfm, accessed 29.01.2026

2.3. Media handling protocols

Before responding to any media inquiry (including journalists, press offices, podcasts, or public interviews), partners are requested to contact the project coordination team so as to support the response, ensure alignment with the project objectives, and verify that no confidential or sensitive information is disclosed as seen fit.

Requests for interviews, quotes or public statements related to the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project should be submitted to the coordination team in advance for revision of their appropriateness to the content, and, when necessary, consult internally before granting approval. If a sensitive topic is involved, strategic implications, or high public visibility, the coordination may also involve the Project Officer to align with Horizon Europe communication practices.

Joint social media posts and coordinated announcements should be channeled via the project's official communication channels (i.e. LinkedIn and BlueSky); this is to ensure consistency and avoid duplication. All publication pieces are encouraged to align with key messages, and the visual identity of the project, as described in previous sections and within the section relating to Social Media in Deliverable 1.1. All communication pieces should include the European Innovation Council logo and statement, the latter wherever possible.

3. Conclusion

The guidelines and recommendations presented in this report are intended to safeguard the project's credibility, ensure consistent messaging to the intended audiences, and support the effective dissemination of the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project's general information and results.

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Innovation
Council

**Funded by
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